

Cohort Effect in Mortality from HIV and Tuberculosis in Russia

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Abstract

This study examines long-term trends in mortality from HIV infection and tuberculosis in Russia. We use age-specific mortality data for men and women from the Russian Fertility and Mortality Database (RusFMD/RosBRiS) of the NES Center for Demographic Research for the period 1989–2022. Based on these data, cohort mortality rates were calculated, and an age–period–cohort (APC) model was constructed. The results show a steady decline in the cohort effect on tuberculosis mortality in both sexes starting with cohorts born in the late 1970s. In contrast, for HIV infection the cohort effect indicates higher mortality risks among women compared to men, while the period effect remains similar for both sexes. The reduction in HIV mortality observed after 2017 does not reflect improved cohort characteristics among younger generations, but rather the influence of situational factors, primarily expanded access to antiretroviral therapy. These findings suggest that the HIV epidemic has moved beyond its initial high-risk birth cohorts of 1975–1985 and now poses a significant threat to younger cohorts, particularly women.

Keywords

infectious diseases, HIV mortality, tuberculosis mortality, generations, age–period–cohort (APC) model, cohort effect

JEL codes: I14, J11, J10

Introduction

The shift from infectious diseases to chronic non-communicable conditions as the leading causes of morbidity and mortality is the defining feature of the second epidemiological transition (Omran 1971). In Russia, this transition was largely completed by the late 1960s: the rapid spread of antibiotics and improved access to healthcare contributed to a

sharp decline in the proportion of deaths from infectious causes. However, following the dissolution of the USSR, an opposite trend emerged. Mortality from infectious diseases began to affect younger age groups. Between 1960 and 2010, the average age at death from infectious causes declined by 8.4 years among men and by 6.3 years among women (Vishnevsky 2015).

HIV infection and tuberculosis currently constitute the main components of infectious mortality in Russia. Whereas tuberculosis dominated at the beginning of the 21st century, by the 2020s HIV had become the leading cause of infection-related deaths in most working-age groups. HIV mortality increased steadily until 2017 for both sexes (Astrelin 2020), after which it began to decline. Nevertheless, mortality from infectious diseases remains higher among women than it was in the early 2000s.

A substantial body of research has examined the determinants of HIV mortality, including gender-specific factors (Pokrovskaya et al. 2014, Pokrovskaya et al. 2016; Pokrovsky et al. 2017; Shestakova 2017; Astrelin 2020; Kossova 2020; Ivanova 2021; Nikolaev 2025). Most studies highlight the role of transmission routes, prevention measures, and access to treatment. A key driver of the post-2017 decline is the expansion of antiretroviral therapy (ART) coverage (Ladnaia et al. 2022; Tsybikova et al. 2024).

However, there are also hypotheses suggesting that changes in HIV mortality may be influenced by cohort effects. Shchur et al. argue that the observed decline may partly reflect the aging of birth cohorts most affected by HIV – those born in 1975–1985 – as they shift from ages 30–44 to 45–59 (Shchur et al. 2023: 26; Belyakov et al. 2015). This raises the question of whether the downward trend can persist in younger cohorts who continue to face substantial infection risks.

Previous studies have indeed identified a cohort effect in the mortality of the generations mentioned in the work of A.E. Shchur (Pustovalov 2015; Maximov 2025). However, the decline in mortality from HIV and other infectious diseases observed at the end of the first quarter of the 21st century may be driven not by a weakening of the cohort effect, but rather by favorable period factors. The cohort effect itself may persist, as has been observed in other countries, such as China (Gao et al. 2020; Wu et al. 2025).

Tuberculosis, a disease that frequently accompanies HIV infection (Tsybikova 2022), also warrants examination in this context. It is therefore important to establish whether mortality from tuberculosis exhibits similar cohort-specific patterns or whether its decline primarily reflects improvements in treatment and prevention, as well as the fact that many tuberculosis-related deaths occur among HIV-positive individuals and are statistically recorded as HIV deaths (Minaeva and Vaisman 2015).

Thus, the aim of this study is to compare age-specific mortality patterns for HIV and tuberculosis and to identify period and cohort effects in mortality from these causes among men and women.

Data and methods

This study uses age-specific mortality rates for five-year age groups of men and women in Russia obtained from the Russian Fertility and Mortality Database (RusFMD/RosBRiS) of the NES Center for Demographic Research. Mortality from HIV infection was analyzed for the period 1999–2022 (code 44 in the 1999–2010 classification and code 43 in the 2011–2022 classification), as HIV began to spread widely only in the early 2000s (Astrelin 2020).

Mortality from tuberculosis was examined for a longer period – 1989–2022 – as mortality from infectious diseases rose sharply throughout the 1990s following the dissolution of the USSR (Nechaeva 2017; Kossova 2020). The corresponding causes of death codes include 9–13 in the Soviet classification of 1989–1998, 9–15 in the 1999–2010 classification, and 9–11 in the 2011–2022 classification.

Five-year age-specific mortality rates were first converted into death counts using mid-year population estimates for corresponding age groups. The resulting death counts were then interpolated into single-year age categories using cubic monotonic interpolation, consistent with established methodology in the Human Mortality Database (Wilmoth et al. 2025).

Cohort mortality rates were calculated as the arithmetic mean of age-specific mortality rates for adjacent ages and years. This method is valid under two main assumptions: (1) mortality rates for adjacent birth cohorts within the same calendar year are similar, and (2) mortality rates remain relatively stable between adjacent calendar years (Andreev 2016).

Standardized mortality rates (SMRs) were calculated using the direct standardization method, with the age distribution of the female population of Russia in 1999 used as the standard. The female population was selected because its age structure is more stable over time compared with that of the male population or the total population.

To identify cohort effects, we applied an age–period–cohort (APC) model specified in our previous research (Maximov 2025). The model can be written as:

$$m = f(a) + h(c) + g(p),$$

where m is age-specific mortality rate, a is age, c is year of birth (cohort), p is year of death (period). The function $f(a)$ represents the age effect, $h(c)$ the cohort effect, and $g(p)$ the period effect.

In the model, the age effect function $f(a)$ reflects age-specific mortality in the reference cohort. The cohort born in 1975 was chosen as the reference, as previous studies indicate that cohorts born in the late 1970s and early 1980s experienced the highest mortality risks associated with the HIV epidemic in Russia (Pustovalov 2015; Maximov 2025). The cohort effect function $h(c)$ is interpreted as the log rate ratio of mortality in a given cohort relative to the reference cohort. The period effect function $g(p)$ captures the residual variation unexplained by age and cohort effects, representing period-specific influences (also expressed as rate ratios).

The APC analysis was limited to ages 20 and older because mortality from HIV and tuberculosis at younger ages is extremely low. In such age groups, even small absolute fluctuations in mortality can produce substantial distortions in APC estimates.

Results and discussion

Among men, mortality from tuberculosis remained higher than mortality from HIV infection from 1999 to 2015, and among women this pattern persisted until 2013 (Figure 1). Tuberculosis mortality has been steadily declining in both sexes since around 2005. In contrast, mortality from HIV continued to rise until 2017–2019, after which a gradual decline began. By 2018, mortality from HIV among women had already exceeded mortality from tuberculosis among men.

Figure 2 demonstrates that the growth of HIV mortality among women was consistently faster than among men throughout the study period. Previous research has not identified

major sex-specific differences in the demographic or behavioral characteristics of individuals dying from HIV that could fully explain this trend. Therefore, gender differences in mortality dynamics are likely driven by generational patterns and the life-course context of the affected cohorts (Astrelin 2020; Ivanova 2021).

Figure 1. Standardized mortality rates from tuberculosis and HIV among men and women in Russia, per 1.000.000 population. *Source:* Author’s calculations based on data from the Russian Fertility and Mortality Database (RusFMD/RosBRiS).

Figure 2. Five-year rate of change in standardized mortality from HIV infection and tuberculosis among men and women in Russia. *Source:* Author’s calculations based on data from the Russian Fertility and Mortality Database (RusFMD/RosBRiS).

The structure of mortality from infectious diseases (Figure 3) also demonstrates that at all ages female mortality from HIV increased more rapidly than male mortality, particularly in contrast to mortality from tuberculosis. In the 25–29 age group, the HIV mortality rate among women rose almost monotonically until 2017, whereas among men the rate in this age group in the mid-2010s was even lower than in the mid-2000s. By 2022, the contribution of tuberculosis to infectious mortality had significantly decreased across all age groups.

Among men, mortality from infectious diseases declined across all age groups between 1999 and 2022. In contrast, among women – with the exception of the 20–24 and 25–29 age groups – infectious mortality increased: it doubled in the 30–34 and 35–39 age groups, increased 2.5–3 times in the 40–44 age group, and nearly quadrupled in the 45–49 age group. Thus, whereas infectious diseases historically affected men more severely – particularly by the end of the second epidemiological transition – the HIV epidemic has become an increasingly critical cause of premature mortality among women.

Furthermore, cohorts born in the mid-1970s, who reached ages 45–49 by the late 2010s, exhibited notably elevated HIV mortality in this period compared with other generations.

Figure 3. Composition of mortality from infectious diseases among men and women in Russia by selected age groups, per 1,000,000 population. *Source:* Author’s calculations based on data from the Russian Fertility and Mortality Database (RusFMD/RosBRiS).

Age profiles of cohort-specific HIV mortality rates (Figure 4) reveal notable differences between men and women. Among men, the cohort with the highest age-specific mortality curve was born in 1978, whereas among women it was the 1981 cohort. For male cohorts born after 1980, mortality at younger ages is similar to or lower than that of the 1980 cohort.

In contrast, among female cohorts, later generations exhibit higher mortality at young ages: the 1985 cohort shows elevated rates between ages 25 and 32, and the 1990 cohort between ages 22 and 30.

These patterns suggest that observed gender differences in the dynamics of HIV mortality are largely driven by cohort-specific characteristics rather than by period effects alone.

Figure 4. Cohort-specific HIV mortality rates in selected generations in Russia. *Source:* Author's calculations based on data from the Russian Fertility and Mortality Database (RusFMD/RosBRiS).

Age profiles of cohort-specific tuberculosis mortality rates (Figure 5) also reveal notable gender differences. Among men born in 1970, each subsequent cohort exhibits a lower age-specific mortality profile. At ages up to 30, the 1970 cohort shows slightly lower mortality than the immediately following cohorts; however, at older ages, age-specific mortality rates are higher than those of subsequent generations. For the cohort born in 1990, mortality between ages 20 and 31 is nearly constant across ages.

Figure 5. Cohort-specific tuberculosis mortality rates in selected generations in Russia. *Source:* Author's calculations based on data from the Russian Fertility and Mortality Database (RusFMD/RosBRiS).

Among women, the highest age-specific mortality rates are observed in cohorts born between 1980 and 1985, with peaks occurring in the same calendar period (mid-2010s). The age at which the maximum mortality occurs differs by approximately one year across these cohorts. In later cohorts, mortality at younger ages is elevated, but the peak mortality is lower than in preceding generations.

These patterns suggest that the 1990s, a period of widespread tuberculosis and HIV transmission, may have had a stronger impact on women’s health, contributing to a faster rise in HIV mortality and a slower decline in tuberculosis mortality among women during the first quarter of the 21st century.

Figures 6–8 present the results of the APC analysis of mortality from HIV and tuberculosis.

The age effects (Figure 6) differ between tuberculosis and HIV. For tuberculosis, the age effect rises until approximately age 40 and then declines, with the male curve consistently higher than the female curve. This pattern confirms that tuberculosis remains primarily a “male” and “younger” cause of death (Astrelin 2020).

In contrast, the age effect for HIV mortality increases almost exponentially. Among men up to age 75, the age effect is higher than among women across all ages. While the excess male age effect is clear, the apparent exponential increase may partially reflect a statistical artifact: HIV mortality at older ages is currently low, and it remains uncertain how mortality will evolve in the cohorts born in the 1970s as they age. Nonetheless, similar age-effect patterns have been reported in studies of HIV cohort effects in China (Ren et al. 2022). The increase in the age effect can also be explained biologically, as older HIV patients are more vulnerable to chronic conditions, particularly circulatory and endocrine diseases (Wing 2016; Mpondo 2016).

Figure 6. Age effects on HIV and tuberculosis mortality among men and women in Russia (generation born in 1975), per 1.000.000 population. *Source:* Author’s calculations based on data from the Russian Fertility and Mortality Database (RusFMD/RosBRiS).

The period effects (Figure 7) for both sexes are virtually identical for HIV and tuberculosis mortality.

For tuberculosis, the period effect rises until approximately 2005 and then begins to decline. In the early 2000s, the Russian government implemented intensive state-level programs aimed at the prevention and treatment of socially significant diseases, including tuberculosis (Skachkova et al. 2008; Shkolnikov et al. 2014; Shestakova 2017). A 2014 study demonstrated a positive relationship between the effectiveness of anti-tuberculosis services and reductions in tuberculosis mortality (Mikhaylova et al. 2014).

For HIV, the period effect increased until 2010, remained high until 2017, and then began to decline. By 2018, a downward trend in HIV standardized death rates was also observed (Figure 1), which researchers attribute to improvements in prevention, awareness, and behavior among the younger population (Savina et al. 2023). The decline in the period effect may also reflect the expanding coverage of antiretroviral therapy (ART); by 2020, 53% of HIV patients in Russia were receiving treatment (Yurin et al. 2021).

It is important to note that up to 20% of tuberculosis patients are co-infected with HIV, and in 2014, up to 50% of HIV-related deaths occurred among individuals with concurrent tuberculosis, gradually decreasing to 35% by 2020 (Tsybikova 2022). Mortality statistics are recorded based on the underlying cause of death listed on death certificates; in cases of co-infection, HIV is registered as the underlying cause regardless of the presence of tuberculosis (Minaeva and Vaisman 2015; Letter of the Ministry of Health 2016). Therefore, the decline in the tuberculosis period effect against a relatively high and stable HIV period effect in the early 2010s may partly reflect the high proportion of patients with both diseases.

Figure 7. Period effects on HIV and tuberculosis mortality among men and women in Russia, expressed as the rate ratio relative to the reference cohort. *Source:* Author's calculations based on data from the Russian Fertility and Mortality Database (RusFMD/RosBRIS).

Cohort effects on HIV and tuberculosis mortality (Figure 8) exhibit substantial variation. For tuberculosis, each successive male cohort shows a lower risk of death, reflecting improvements in preventive measures and diagnostic capabilities over time. Among women, the cohort effect is relatively stable, though cohorts born between 1975 and 1980 exhibit values above 1. This pattern corresponds to a slight increase in female tuberculosis mortality observed until the mid-2000s (Figure 1). During this period, mortality among younger women (ages 20–24 and 25–29) also increased (Figure 3), suggesting that adverse economic conditions during adolescence in the 1990s negatively affected young women. Additionally,

during the 2000s, the average age at first tuberculosis diagnosis gradually increased, while the average age of death from the disease decreased (Kozlov and Ramonov 2011). Thus, women born in the late 1970s experienced higher tuberculosis incidence than previous generations, and delayed diagnosis likely contributed to elevated mortality in these cohorts.

The cohort effect on HIV mortality rises monotonically for both sexes, with the increase being more pronounced among women than men. This difference may be attributed to distinct transmission routes: in the late 1990s, HIV spread predominantly through intravenous drug use, primarily affecting men (Pokrovsky et al. 2017). Since 2002, heterosexual transmission has become increasingly prevalent, bringing more women into the epidemic. HIV infection also occurs at younger ages among women than men (Pokrovskaja et al. 2014, Pokrovskaya et al. 2016), which may explain the higher cohort effect observed among later-born female generations.

Notably, the higher cohort effect among women in Russia contrasts with patterns observed in other countries. For example, in China, male cohorts exhibit higher HIV cohort effects (Gao et al. 2020; Wu et al. 2025). This difference is likely due to the timing and main transmission routes: in China, heterosexual and homosexual contact has been the dominant mode of HIV transmission since the start of the epidemic, so female cohorts did not experience the same rapid initial exposure.

Figure 8. Cohort effects on HIV and tuberculosis mortality among men and women in Russia, expressed as the rate ratio relative to the reference cohort (logarithmic scale). *Source:* Author’s calculations based on data from the Russian Fertility and Mortality Database (RusFMD/RosBRiS).

Thus, the decline in HIV mortality during the first quarter of the 21st century does not reflect a weaker cohort effect among generations born after 1985. Instead, favorable period effects – particularly the expansion of antiretroviral therapy (ART) coverage (Tsybikova et al. 2024) – have mitigated the high cohort effect in intergenerational mortality.

Of particular concern is the rapid growth of the cohort effect among women. Continued HIV infections at young ages could adversely affect reproductive outcomes in Russia. Women living with HIV tend to have fewer children on average (Pokrovskaya et al. 2016), and the indirect economic losses from HIV are substantial due to mortality among women of reproductive age (Podymova et al. 2018). Although previous studies report no gender differences in the profiles of those who died from HIV (Ivanova 2021), women in Russia currently constitute a high-risk group, especially given that heterosexual contact is now the dominant route of transmission.

While the epidemic initially affected generations born in the late 1970s and early 1980s (Belyakov et al. 2015), it has since expanded beyond this initial focus and now increasingly affects younger cohorts. Another factor contributing to the higher cohort effect among women may be the higher detection rate of HIV infection in women of reproductive age, as they undergo mandatory HIV testing when registering for prenatal care at women's clinics.

The study has several limitations. First, the analysis does not include individuals under 20 years of age. Mortality from HIV and tuberculosis in these age groups is relatively low, so their exclusion is unlikely to substantially bias the results.

Second, HIV only began spreading widely in Russia at the end of the 20th century, which means that APC models may yield less reliable estimates due to the relatively short time series.

Third, age–period–cohort analysis is strictly valid only for closed populations. A standard APC assumption from a migration perspective is that the characteristics and mortality patterns of migrants are equivalent to those of the native population. Accounting for the migration status of the deceased – at least by place of birth – could address this limitation. Although the place of birth is recorded on the medical death certificate stub (Order of the Ministry of Health 2021), the database of medical certificates is not publicly available. Therefore, APC estimates should be interpreted with caution, as population heterogeneity may distort age, period, and cohort effects. Notably, all foreign nationals applying for work permits in Russia must provide proof of HIV-negative status, so most foreign migrants are likely infected domestically.

Fourth, the epidemiological dynamics of HIV and tuberculosis vary across regions of Russia (Astrelin 2020; Savina et al. 2023). Accordingly, a more detailed regional analysis would be appropriate and represents a promising avenue for future research.

Conclusion

Mortality from socially significant diseases, namely HIV and tuberculosis, remains high, particularly among older working-age groups. In the context of the spread of drug-resistant forms of tuberculosis, especially among patients co-infected with HIV, simultaneous prevention of both diseases assumes critical importance (Tsybikova and Lapshina 2023).

As an independent disease, tuberculosis is becoming less prominent in the structure of infectious mortality, and the cohort effect in tuberculosis mortality is steadily declining.

Generations born in the late 1970s exhibit the highest cohort effect, supporting the hypothesis that these cohorts were disproportionately affected.

The study demonstrates that the cohort effect on HIV mortality continues to rise, with each successive generation facing higher mortality risks, particularly women. While HIV was primarily a “male” problem in the 1990s, by the 2000s and 2010s the epidemic shifted toward heterosexual transmission, affecting women of reproductive age. The observed decline in HIV mortality after 2017 is largely attributable to period factors – such as expanded access to therapy and improved diagnostics – rather than a reduction in the underlying cohort-specific risk among generations entering working age.

These findings confirm that the HIV epidemic continues to evolve, affecting not only the cohorts initially impacted in the 1990s but also younger generations. In contrast, the tuberculosis epidemic has largely receded. Given the current situation, public health interventions should focus on cohorts born after 1990 to prevent further spread of HIV among these generations.

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